

DEVELOPING THE ACTIVITY OF JOINT STOCK COMPANIES BY IMPROVING DIVIDEND POLICY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10673199>

Abstract: In this article, it is said that effective dividend practices can motivate not only foreign capital, but also the national capital market to attract a high amount of capital and make dividend practices a primary issue in relations with investors in the periods before and after public placement of shares.

Keywords: dividend policy, dividend payments, joint-stock companies and shares.

Globally, leading rating agencies, auditing companies and consulting companies are analyzing the history of dividends, dividend forecasts for companies and their impact on share prices in connection with the dividend payments of companies in the world. It is these aspects that require regular improvement of the dividend policy in joint-stock companies at the national and international level.

In scientific studies of world practice, dividend policy in joint-stock companies, analysis of dividend payments, investment attractiveness, the integral relationship between dividend payments and share price, the importance of dividend policy for the impact on the financial condition of minority and majority shareholders are constant attention. are important issues. In recent years, the relationship between independent directors and dividend policy, the influence of gender equality on the board of directors on dividend policy, the degree of influence of dividend payment forms on stock liquidity, the influence of environmental pollution on dividend policy, it means that there is a need for more extensive research on the consideration of dividend policy in business strategy, the assessment of the level of influence of cross-border mergers and acquisitions on dividend policy, and the effective organization of financial relations with investors after a successful global public offering of shares.

In Uzbekistan, by the end of 2026, "In order to increase financial resources in the economy, the turnover of the stock market will increase from 200 million US dollars to 7 billion in the next 5 years." Delivery to the US dollar" is set as a

priority goal. In order to achieve this, large-scale privatization and a sharp increase in the share of the private sector in bank assets are expected. But for this, the issue of ensuring investment attractiveness by regular dividend payments in joint-stock companies is important, but in most cases it is neglected. It is known that at least 50 percent of the net profit achieved by economic companies with a state share in the charter capital of more than 50 percent must be allocated to dividends, although it is determined by the laws on the state budget by year. the fact that exceptions are given to some enterprises leads to the non-provision of the interests of minority shareholders. It should also be noted that national issuers do not pay attention to the issue of effective and mutually beneficial organization of relations with investors through dividends after the preparation and practice of public placement of shares (IPO, SPO).

In international practice, four main types of dividends are distinguished, which are used and paid in the form of money. They are "regular cash dividends, additional dividends, special dividends, and liquidating dividends." From the point of view of dividend payment forms in international practice, companies not only pay in cash but also in the form of shares, increase the demand of small investors by crushing shares, conduct a dividend policy as a result of announcing the repurchase of shares, and have a positive effect on the market. they also implement dividend policy by signaling. In this case, after the dividend is paid in cash, the share price will decrease. When decisions are made about stock splits and share buybacks, stock prices rise. As a result, shareholders receive income from the positive difference in the share price, not as a dividend.

If we pay attention to the dividends of the Coca-Cola company, first of all, the regularity of dividend payments attracts our attention. From the table above, we can see that from the end of the second quarter of 1987 to the end of the first quarter of 2023, the Coca-Cola Company regularly paid dividends on a quarterly basis. The amount of dividend per share was 0.51 US dollars, the highest for the fourth quarter of 2011 and the first quarter of 2012. The lowest dividend was paid at the end of three quarters of 1996 at 0.125 US dollars.

Regular dividends are also being paid priority attention by the Apple company. This is shown by the analysis of dividend payments made from the end of the first quarter of 1987 to the end of the first quarter of 2023. Also, in the company's 35-year dividend history, it is possible to witness that dividend practices have been applied 5 times by crushing shares.

The dividend history of the analyzed Coca-Cola and Apple companies shows that both of them prioritize paying regular quarterly dividends in cash. It

should be noted here that this aspect is characteristic of the Anglo-Saxon model of the financial market. Also, in this model, strict conditions regarding information openness apply, and financial reports and analytical reviews are published quarterly. Strict disclosure requirements and quarterly dividend payments provide these companies with free advertising. We should also note that the fact that these dividend analyzes have been given for 35 years in both companies has served to form the dividend history.

If we focus on the dividend analysis of Japanese companies that have a place in the financial market and the world economy, then the company's dividend analysis for 2009-2022 shows that the company made dividend payments based on every six-month reporting period. is showing. And it is noteworthy that this order was strictly followed. The highest such dividend was \$2.45 at the end of the second quarter of 2020. It is clear from the above table that the dividend payments of Mercedes-Benz Group, which has its place in the world automotive industry, were made at the end of the financial year. It is also significant that the highest dividend at the end of 2021 was paid on May 4, 2022 at 5 euros per share. Even in this case, dividends can be recognized as regular dividends.

Special attention paid by foreign companies to paying regular dividends served the active development of the stock market in the countries where they operate. Based on this aspect, it is appropriate to pay special attention to regular dividends in countries, especially in our republic.

In general, it should be noted that the ratio of the amount allocated to the dividend to the achieved net profit is a matter of constant attention of shareholders and investors. In this regard, dividend stability based on market returns for financial reporting periods and regular growth based on net profit is extremely important in today's fierce competition. This aspect also serves as a basis for joint-stock companies to enter the global financial markets. We should note that regular dividend payments are directly related to the financing strategy of joint-stock companies.

At first glance, the conflict of interests, the conflict of interests of shareholders and hired management in the distribution of profits appears to be a natural situation. But the inability to ensure the balance of interests in this case leads to the escalation of corporate conflicts related to the distribution of profits and causes a decrease in investment attractiveness.

If the share of private shareholders is high in a joint-stock company, and purely corporate financial management is applied, in such a case, the conflict of

interests with hired management is regulated by the theory of contracts. These aspects, in turn, serve to ensure the distribution of profits and investment attractiveness.

As we have said in conclusion, the development of activities of joint-stock companies and their gaining influence in the global market in many ways directly depends on their global competitiveness. For this, it is necessary to improve the finances of joint-stock companies, in particular, their financial support. At the same time that shares have been seen as a cheap financial resource in international practice for centuries, we cannot say that this opportunity is being used sufficiently in our country. It should be noted here that one of the main reasons for this is the lack of improvement of the dividend policy.

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